

Review

Fighting antibiotic resistance in the local management of bovine mastitis

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ABSTRACT

Bovine mastitis is a widespread infectious disease with a significant economic burden, accounting for 80 % of the antibiotic usage in dairy animals. In recent years, extensive research has focused on using biomimetic approaches such as probiotics, bacteriocins, bacteriophages, or phytochemicals as potential alternatives to antibiotics. The local administration of therapeutic molecules through the intramammary route is one of the most commonly strategies to manage bovine mastitis. This review highlights the most important findings in this field and discusses their local application in mastitis therapy. In contrast to antibiotics, the proposed alternatives are not limited to promote bacterial death but consider other factors associated to the host microenvironments. To this end, the proposed biomimetic strategies can modulate different stages of infection by modifying the local microbiota, preventing oxidative stress, reducing bacterial adhesion to epithelial cells, modulating the immune response, or mediating the inflammatory process. Numerous *in vitro* studies support the antimicrobial, anti-biofilm or antioxidant properties of these alternatives. However, *in vivo* studies incorporating these components within pharmaceutical formulations with potential clinical application are limited. The development of secure, stable, and effective drug delivery systems based on the proposed options is necessary to achieve real alternatives to antibiotics in the clinic.

1. Introduction

The One Health Action Plan against antimicrobial resistance (AMR) initiated by the European Union (EU) in 2017 highlighted the link between human and animal health. Therefore, approaches to manage AMR should consider both equally [1]. On the other hand, according to the World Health Organisation (WHO) animals consume twice the amount of antibiotics of humans, making livestock farming a sector that requires urgent actions [2,3].

The dairy industry is a significant contributor to the livestock sector. In 2020, the EU produced 160.1 million tonnes of raw milk, predominantly sourced from dairy cows. Currently, there are an estimated 1.7 million farms across the EU, collectively housing 23.5 million dairy cows. Over a lactation period of 10 months, each cow produces an average of 25Kg of milk per day [4].

Bovine mastitis is a disease characterized by inflammation of the mammary gland and udder tissues due to trauma, chemical irritation, or infection by various microorganisms, including fungi, viruses, algae and

especially bacteria [5,6]. It is one of the most prevalent diseases in the dairy industry, affecting 40 % of cows in herds. This condition poses a significant economic burden, costing over 185€/cow per year in the EU and rising to \$35 billion worldwide [5,7]. These losses can be attributed to various factors, including reduced milk production, diminished milk quality, discarded milk, veterinary expenses, and premature culling of cows [5].

As bacterial infections stand as the primary cause of bovine mastitis, antibiotics have been the mainstay of treatment for decades [8]. Astonishingly, around 80 % of antibiotics employed in the dairy industry are dedicated to control and treat mastitis [9]. They are usually administered through two routes: parenteral and, most commonly, intramammary (IMM). The local administration of therapeutic molecules through IMM route offers several advantages for mastitis treatment in dairy cows, allowing high local drug concentrations with minimal systemic absorption reducing undesired side effects [10]. However, considering the current scenario, the pressing needs to mitigate the development of AMR demand a shift away from the excessive antibiotic

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usage associated to bovine mastitis management. Therefore, it is essential to explore innovative non-antibiotic strategies that can effectively prevent or treat bovine mastitis [6].

This review aims at identifying and discussing the main strategies pointed out to manage bovine mastitis through local administration avoiding antibiotic use. Several approaches are currently under development. These alternatives are not only focused on promoting bacterial death, but also consider the infection as a broken equilibrium between the host and the bacteria. Therefore, this review highlights and discusses the latest findings, encompassing research conducted from 2018 to the present. A deep literature review was performed to elucidate the mechanism of action followed to restore the homeostasis of the identified strategies. Moreover, clinical efficacy of the developed approaches and future perspectives of bovine mastitis management have also been discussed.

2. Current research lines on non-antibiotic alternatives

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in research aimed at discovering non-antibiotic alternatives for the management of bovine mastitis. The literature reveals that most of them are based on biomimetic approaches, taking inspiration from the resources used by organisms to maintain homeostasis, defend themselves or survive. As summarize in Fig. 1, these options include probiotics, bacteriocins, phytochemicals (plant extracts and essential oils) and bacteriophages. In addition, recent studies have explored innovative options, such as nanoparticles and antimicrobial peptides of non-bacterial origin [11–13].

2.1. Searching for homeostasis: Probiotics

Probiotics are “live microorganisms which, when administered in adequate amounts, confer a health benefit on the host” [14]. They exert their beneficial effects through different mechanisms as the modification of the local microbiota composition or acting directly on pathogenic microorganisms. Probiotics can adhere and interact with epithelial cells, improving their barrier and promoting cell renewal. Moreover, they can also enhance the host immune system response [15,16].

Probiotics are Generally Recognised as Safe (GRAS) products and widely used in the food industry as preservatives. Among them, lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are the best-known and most widely used [17,18]. These Gram-positive bacteria, primarily belonging to the genera *Lactobacillus* (Lb.), *Lactococcus* (Lc.), *Bifidobacterium*, and *Streptococcus*, have been *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluated for bovine mastitis prevention or therapy.

Several *in vitro* studies were performed to assess the interaction between probiotics and pathogenic microorganisms or mammary epithelial cells, and to examine their impact on the immune response (Table 1).

Table 1

Summary of *in vitro* studies carried out with probiotics on pathogens of bovine mastitis or epithelial cells.

Probiotic species	Pathogens	Results	Reference
Lb. * and Lc. * *strains	-	Cell adhesion Biofilm forming ability	[26]
Lb. *casei	<i>S. aureus</i>	Anti-inflammatory Immunomodulatory potential	[22]
Lb. *rhamnosus; Lb. *plantarum; Lb. *brevis; Lb. *plantarum; Lb. *plantarum	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. xylosum</i> ; <i>S. epidermidis</i>	Antibiofilm Biofilm forming ability (<i>Lb. rhamnosus</i> ; <i>Lb. plantarum</i> 2/37)	[21]
Lc. * * lactis; Lb. *perolens	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. dysgalactiae</i>	Cell adhesion Bacteriostatic	[24]
Lb. *acidophilus	<i>E. coli</i>	Anti-inflammatory properties	[27]
Lb. * sakei	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. agalactiae</i> ; <i>S. dysgalactiae</i>	Antibacterial Antibiofilm	[25]
Lb. * rhamnosus	<i>E. coli</i>	Apoptosis improvement Reduction of inflammation	[19]
Lb. *plantarum	<i>E. coli</i>	Antibacterial Reduction of inflammation	[28]
LAB strains	<i>S. aureus</i>	Cell adhesion Bacteriostatic	[30]
Lb. *rhamnosus	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	Pathogen reduction Cytoprotective	[20]
Lb. *plantarum	<i>E. coli</i>	Reduction of inflammation	[29]
Lb. *perolens; Lc. * * lactis	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. chromogenes</i> ; <i>S. uberis</i> ; <i>E. coli</i>	Reduction of pathogen adhesion	[23]

*Lactobacillus (Lb.);

* *Lactococcus (Lc.).

Species, such as *Lb. rhamnosus*, *Lb. casei*, or *Lc. lactis*, have shown activity against different bacteria, especially *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus* [19–24].

Certain LAB have also demonstrated significant potential in treating persistent infections by pathogenic bacteria biofilm elimination or replacement [21,25,26]. As an example, *Lb. rhamnosus* and *Lb. plantarum*, have been found to replace the biofilms of *S. aureus*, *S. xylosum* and *S. epidermidis* [21]. Additionally, *Lb. sakei* has demonstrated antibiofilm activity against *S. aureus*, *S. agalactiae* and *S. dysgalactiae* [25].

Additionally, the antimicrobial activity of some LAB as *Lb. casei* has been associated with the inhibition of adhesion and internalization of the pathogen to epithelial cells [22]. Other species also modulate the immune response and mediate the endothelial cells inflammatory process. This has been demonstrated with *Lb. casei*, *Lb. acidophilus* and *Lb. plantarum* on bovine mammary epithelial cells (BMEC) [22,27–29] and also with *Lb. rhamnosus* strains in bovine mammary alveolar epithelial cells (MAC-T). In this case, it was shown that *Lb. rhamnosus* decreases apoptosis, reduces cytokine levels, and increases IL-10 mRNA expression in infections caused by *E. coli* [19]. *Lb. rhamnosus* also reduces cell damage by protecting cell to cell tight junctions and decreases NLRP3 inflammasome activation, regulating the inflammatory response caused by *Bacillus cereus* infection [20]. Furthermore, strains of *Lc. lactis*, *Lb. plantarum*, *Lb. brevis*, *Lb. paracasei*, *Lb. rhamnosus* or *Lb. perolens* have shown high colonization capacity of BMEC or MAC-T [23,24,26].

In vivo experiments conducted in murine and bovine mastitis models have employed local administration methods. *Lc.* and *Lb.* species have been the focal points of extensive study (Table 2). Across these investigations, milk samples were consistently collected at various intervals, analysing SCC and bacteriological counts.

Studies in a murine model have proved that strains of *Enterococcus mundtii* can inhibit infection and reduce the inflammation in the

Fig. 1. New strategies for local bovine mastitis therapy avoiding AMR.

Table 2
Summary of *in vivo* studies carried out with IMM administration of probiotics in mastitis animal models.

Probiotic species	Animal model	Dose	Sample evaluated	Evaluation time	Pathogens	Results	Reference
<i>Lc. * lactis</i>	Bovine	1×10^9 CFU**	Milk	0, 6, 24, 48, 72, 120 and 168 h	-	SCC*** reduction Anti-inflammatory properties	[33]
<i>Bifidobacterium breve</i>	Bovine	3×10^9 CFU**	Milk	0 h and 14 days	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. uberis</i> ; <i>S. dysgalactiae</i> ; <i>E. coli</i>	SCC*** reduction Pathogen reduction Immune response promotion	[34]
<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	Bovine	1×10^3 or 1×10^9 CFU**	Milk	Every 24 h for 4 or 14 days	<i>S. aureus</i>	SCC*** reduction Pathogen reduction	[35]
<i>Enterococcus mundtii</i>	Murine	1×10^8 CFU**	Mammary tissue	24 h	<i>S. aureus</i>	Reduction of neutrophil infiltration Reduction of inflammation Protection of the mammary gland	[31]
<i>Lb. **** perolens</i> ; <i>Lc. * lactis</i>	Bovine	1.5×10^6 CFU** of each strain	Mammary tissue	48 h	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>S. chromogenes</i> ; <i>S. uberis</i> ; <i>E. coli</i>	Reduction of pathogen adhesion	[23]
<i>Lc. * lactis</i>	Bovine	1×10^9 CFU**	Milk	0, 6, 24, 48, 72, 120 and 168 h	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. uberis</i> ; <i>S. dysgalactiae</i>	SCC*** reduction Pathogen reduction Immunomodulatory potential	[32]

Lactococcus (Lc.)*; **Colony forming units (CFU); *Somatic cell counts (SCC); *****Lactobacillus (Lb.)*.

mammary gland, preventing mastitis. The efficacy of this intervention was unequivocally demonstrated through histological evaluation conducted 24 h post-administration [31].

The inhibitory efficacy of *Lc. Lactis* and *Lb. perolens* against the adhesion of *S. aureus*, *S. chromogenes*, *S. uberis* and *E. coli* to BMEC has also been demonstrated *in vivo*. The combined administration of both strains followed by histological evaluation, confirmed their effectiveness. However, the effect was less pronounced for *S. uberis* and *E. coli*, compared to *in vitro* results [23]. In addition, *Lc. lactis* showed immunomodulatory properties by stimulating defence mechanisms and enhancing the inflammatory response *in vivo* [32].

Moreover, when *Lc. Lactis*, *Bifidobacterium breve* or *Bacillus velezensis* were administered in a bovine mastitis model, they successfully reduced pathogen and somatic cell counts (SCC), while promoting an immune response [33–35].

Overall, these studies point out probiotic strains can inhibit mastitis-causing pathogens, reduce their adhesion and internalization, and regulate the hosts immune response. Relatively standardized doses of probiotics were used, as most trials employ bacteria counts ranging from 10^6 to 10^9 colony forming units (CFU). Although more research is needed, probiotics hold great potential for the treatment and prevention of bovine mastitis.

2.2. Killing as bacteria: bacteriocins

Bacteriocins are small antimicrobial proteins or peptides ribosomally synthesized by Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. They are often released to kill or inhibit the growth of competing bacteria, fungi or viruses, providing a selective advantage [36,37]. The mechanism of action of bacteriocins varies depending on the type and the target bacterium. However, most bacteriocins exert their antimicrobial activity by disrupting cell functions (transcription, translation, replication...) or altering the cell membrane structure (by channels and/or pores) [38].

Bacteriocins, particularly from Gram-positive bacteria, have been extensively studied for their potential as alternatives to antibiotics in the treatment of bacterial infections in the veterinary field, as well as for their use as food preservatives [36,38–40]. They present advantages over other antimicrobials as activity at low concentrations, easily metabolised and capacity of modification by bioengineering techniques. However, they also present limitations related to their size as the incorporation into adequate pharmaceutical formulations and the identification of suitable administration routes. Nanotechnology is being considered as a viable option in this regard [36,37,41,42].

These antimicrobial molecules are classified into four main classes depending on their structure, mode of action, spectrum activity and other characteristics. Lantibiotics or class I bacteriocins are peptides that

contain post-translationally modified amino acids, such as lanthionine. They are characterized by a broad-spectrum activity against Gram-positive bacteria. Class II bacteriocins are small heat-stable non-lantibiotic peptides that have a narrow spectrum of activity, targeting specific bacteria. Class III bacteriocins are large heat-labile proteins that often have a broad spectrum of activity against Gram-negative bacteria. Finally, Class IV bacteriocins are cyclic peptides that have a broad spectrum of activity against both, Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria [31,43].

The most studied bacteriocin is nisin, a lantibiotic produced by *Lc. Lactis*. Nisin has been used as a food preservative since the 1960 s and is currently approved as a food bio-preservative in many countries, including the United States (US) and the EU. It is also approved as an upper disinfectant for the prevention of IMM infections in dairy cattle [44].

Nisin has antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus*, *S. uberis* and *S. dysgalactiae* by interfering with the cell wall synthesis and altering the membrane structure through pore formation [36,39,45]. Unfortunately, several nisin-resistant bacterial strains have already been identified (e.g. *Staphylococcus*). This resistance can be intrinsic or acquired, and involves various mechanisms, including the production of modifying enzymes, efflux pumps, and modifications to the bacterial cell membrane [46]. This fact has led to the search for new bacteriocins or derivatives. Bioengineered nisin derivatives namely nisin A M17Q, A HTK, A T2L or PV exhibit antimicrobial activity against resistant strains and biofilm eradication [45]. The results of these studies are shown in Table 3.

Other LAB bacteriocins, such as bactofencin (produced by *Lb. salivarius*) and reuterin (produced by *Lb. reuteri*) have shown *in vitro* activity against *Staphylococcus* or *Streptococcus* strains isolated from clinical cases of bovine mastitis. The antimicrobial activity of bactofencin is based on the modification of teichoic acids, components of the cell wall, while reuterin acts by inducing oxidative stress through the modification of proteins thiol groups [36]. Furthermore, their IMM administration in an *in vivo* bovine mastitis model, showed a decrease in the bacterial load, proving their potential as teat disinfectants [37].

Staphylococcus or *Streptococcus* strains also produce bacteriocins, which act against competing bacteria, even from the same genus [38, 47]. Aureocin 4181, for example, a staphylococin produced by *S. aureus*, has been found to be effective against a wide range of Gram-positive bacteria, including other strains of *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus*. It disrupts the bacterial membrane, leading to cell death [48,49]. On the other hand, Bovicin HC5, produced by *Streptococcus bovis* HC5, has been found to be effective against a wide range of pathogens with a similar mechanism of action than nisin [50].

Ubericin K (produced by *Enterococcus faecium*) has been found to be effective against *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, and

Table 3
Summary of *in vitro* studies evaluating the potential of bacteriocins against bovine mastitis pathogens.

Bacteriocin	Pathogens	Results / mechanisms of action	Reference
Hycin 4244	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp. including MRSA and VRE	Antibacterial and antibiofilm	[52]
Bacteriocins produced by 206 Staphylococcal strains	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	Bacteriostatic	[53]
<i>S. uberis</i> bacteriocins	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>Enterococcus</i> ; <i>Faecalis</i> ; <i>S. agalactiae</i> ; <i>S. dysgalactiae</i> ; <i>E. coli</i> ; <i>Corynebacterium</i> spp.	Antibacterial	[47]
Cationic nisin/dioctadecyl-dimethylammonium bromide nanoparticles	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp. resistant strains	Bactericidal	[41]
Bovicin HC5	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. agalactiae</i>	Antibacterial	[50]
Aureocin 4181	<i>Staphylococcus</i> ; <i>Streptococcus</i>	Antibacterial by cell membrane disruption	[48,49]
Nisin derivates	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp. resistant strains	Antibacterial	[45]
Nisin PV	<i>S. uberis</i>	Antibiofilm	[45]
Ubericin K	<i>Enterococcus</i> ; <i>Streptococcus</i> ; <i>Listeria</i> ; <i>Lactococcus</i>	Antibacterial by cell membrane disruption	[51]
<i>Staphylococcus agnetis</i> 4244 bacteriocins	44 strains of antibiotic-resistant Gram-positive bacteria	Antibacterial against resistant strains	[54]
non-aureus staphylococci bacteriocins	<i>S. aureus</i>	Effective in modulating virulence genes expression	[55]
Bactofencin and reuterin	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. dysgalactiae</i> ; <i>S. uberis</i>	Antibacterial by modification of teichoic acids of the cell wall (bactofencin) or inducing oxidative stress (reuterin)	[36]
<i>S. agalactiae</i> strains	<i>S. pyogenes</i> ; <i>S. agalactiae</i> ; <i>S. porcinus</i> ; <i>S. uberis</i>	Antibacterial	[38]

S. aureus. As aureocin 4181, it works by disrupting the bacterial cell membrane [51]. Finally, Hycin 4244 (produced by *Streptomyces hygroscopicus*) was effective against a variety of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, including several drug-resistant strains such as methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA) and vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* (VRE). It works by inhibiting bacterial protein synthesis [52].

2.3. Protective power of plants: extracts and essential oils

Plants are a rich source of compounds with antimicrobial, antioxidant, and/or anti-inflammatory properties, which can potentially benefit animal health. These phytochemicals are secondary metabolites implicated in plant defence mechanisms. Alkaloids, terpenes, flavonoids or polyphenols are among the most well-known and studied. They are primarily obtained in the form of extracts (PEs) or essential oils (EOs) [56–59].

PEs are mixtures obtained by extraction with solvents. EOs are

lipophilic and aromatic liquids made up of low molecular weight volatile compounds. Both are obtained from different parts of plants (fruits, roots, seeds, leaves) or from a combination of them, such as pomace or marc. PEs and EOs are rich in a wide variety of components with a potential antibacterial activity, being capable of acting as bacteriostatics and/or bactericides [58,60,61]. In addition, its anti-oxidant properties may contribute to the prevention of oxidative stress that occurs in the mammary glands during mastitis [5].

Although the antimicrobial mechanism of action is not fully elucidated, it is believed to be related to bacterial cell rupture [62]. Gram-positive bacteria are highly susceptible to the effects of PEs and EOs, primarily due to their thinner lipopolysaccharide layer that covers the cell wall [57,63].

Table 4 summarizes the main *in vitro* assays studying PEs and EOs for bovine mastitis. Some of them, such as those extracted from *Kalanchoe* or *Datura stramonium*, have shown antimicrobial activity comparable to commercial antibiotics such as gentamicin [61,64]. Furthermore, PEs derived from *Salvinia auriculata*, *Larrea tridentata* and *Moringa oleifera* [65–67], as well as EOs from *Cuminum cyminum*, *Melissa officinalis* or *Menthae piperitae* have shown potential against antibiotic-resistant *S. aureus* strains, targeting both bacteria and biofilms [60,64–66, 68–71]. In addition, synergistic effects have been observed when PEs or EOs (e.g. EOs from *Melaleuca armillaris*) are administered combined with antibiotics, potentially allowing to reduce their doses while maintaining the same bactericidal effects [60]. Also, the combination of EOs (carvacrol, thymol, *trans*-cinnamaldehyde, eugenol, *p*-cymene, menthol, linalool and citral) with medium-chain fatty acids has shown additive antibacterial activity, warranting further investigation [72,73].

A limited number of *in vitro* studies have explored the effects of phytochemicals on epithelial cell lines in an infectious environment. For instance, EOs from *Malaleuca alternifolia* have shown to enhance BMEC proliferation and reduce the inflammatory response triggered by *S. aureus* [70]. Additionally, moringa extract has demonstrated antibacterial properties by reducing the invasion and adhesion of *E. coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis* and *S. simulans* to MAC-T cells [74].

The number of *in vivo* trials on PEs and EOs-based intramammary formulations is relatively limited compared to pure PEs and EOs *in vitro* investigations. However, these studies validate the antimicrobial potential exhibited by certain PEs and EOs *in vitro* (Table 5). For those trials, milk samples were collected at different times after administration, and SCC and bacteriological count were evaluated to conclude their antibacterial activity.

An IMM formulation containing EOs from *Thymus vulgaris* L., *Thymus serpyllum* L., *Origanum vulgare* L. and *Satureia montana* L., has demonstrated activity against *Staphylococcus* spp., *Streptococcus* spp., *Klebsiella* spp., *Proteus mirabilis*, *E. coli*, *S. uberis* and *Serratia marcescens*. This formulation showed higher effectiveness against Gram-positive bacteria [62]. The synergistic effect between phytochemicals and antibiotics have also been proven by combining *Aloe vera* PE with low concentrations of cloxacillin or ceftiofur in a IMM formulation [86].

Based on these findings, phytochemicals, whether used alone or in combination with other antimicrobials, show great potential as antimicrobial agents for the prevention and treatment of bovine mastitis. However, their full potential remains largely unexplored. The development of pharmaceutical formulations utilizing these natural products could serve as a promising alternative to conventional antibiotic use, with a future-oriented approach. Their implementation is expected to contribute to the reduction of antibiotic usage in mastitis management.

2.4. Using the enemies: bacteriophages and endolysins

Bacteriophages or phages, the most abundant entities on Earth, are viruses that attach to specific receptors on the surface of host bacteria, injecting their genetic material, and replicating within the cell [88]. This replication process ultimately leads to the destruction of the bacteria and the consequent release of the newly formed phages to infect other

Table 4

Summary of *in vitro* assays evaluating the potential of EO* and PE** as alternatives in the treatment of bovine mastitis.

EOs/PEs extracts	Pathogens tested	Results	Reference
<i>Moringa oleifera</i> seed	<i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial	[65]
Moringa	<i>E. coli</i> ; <i>E. faecalis</i> ; <i>S. simulans</i> ; <i>Serratia liquefaciens</i>	Antibacterial Pathogen adhesion reduction	[74]
<i>Malaleuca alternifolia</i> EO*	<i>S. aureus</i>	Anti-inflammatory response Immunomodulatory potential	[70]
Nanoemulsions with <i>Achyrocline satureioides</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial Antibiofilm	[71]
<i>Thymus serpyllum</i> L.; <i>Thymus vulgaris</i> L.	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.; <i>Streptococcus</i> spp.; <i>E. coli</i> ; <i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	Antioxidant Antibacterial	[75]
<i>Salvinia auriculata</i> root	<i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial Antibiofilm	[66]
<i>Panax ginseng</i> PE** + Cephalexin	<i>S. aureus</i>	Bactericidal	[69]
Sorghum	<i>E. coli</i> ; <i>Salmonella Typhimurium</i> ; <i>Campylobacter jejuni</i> ; <i>Campylobacter coli</i> ; <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> ; <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ; <i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i> ; <i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>E. faecalis</i>	Antibacterial	[63]
Cinnamon EO* + silver nanoparticles	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	Bactericidal Antibiofilm	[76]
<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> L. EO*	<i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial against resistant strains	[68]
<i>Salvia officinalis</i> ; <i>Satureja hortensis</i> EO*	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. agalactiae</i> ; <i>E. coli</i>	Antibacterial	[77]
<i>Larrea tridentata</i>	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> ; <i>E. coli</i> ; <i>Bacillus cereus</i> ; <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ; <i>Pasteurella multocida</i>	Antibacterial	[67]
<i>Quercus robur</i> + <i>Calluna vulgaris</i> L.	<i>E. coli</i> ; <i>S. agalactiae</i> ; <i>S. uberis</i> ; <i>Serratia liquefaciens</i> ; <i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial	[78]
<i>Ricinus communis</i> leaf	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. agalactiae</i> ; <i>S. pyogenes</i> ; <i>E. coli</i> ; <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ; <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Antibacterial	[79]
<i>Kalanchoe densiflora</i> ; <i>Kalanchoe marmorata</i> ; <i>Datura stramonium</i> ; <i>Clerodandrum myricoides</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	Higher antibacterial activity than gentamicin	[64]
EO* and PE** of <i>Mentha pulegium</i> L.; <i>Nepeta cataria</i> L.; <i>Melissa officinalis</i> L.	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>E. coli</i>	Higher antibacterial activity than some antibiotics	[61]
<i>Melaleuca armillaris</i> EO*	<i>S. aureus</i>	Synergistic bactericidal effect with erythromycin	[60]

Table 4 (continued)

EOs/PEs extracts	Pathogens tested	Results	Reference
EO* + medium-chain fatty acids	<i>S. aureus</i> , <i>E. coli</i> , <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ; <i>S. agalactiae</i>	Antibacterial activity Carvacrol and octanoic acid showed the most synergistic effect	[72,73]
<i>Malaleuca alternifolia</i> EO*	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.; <i>Streptococcus</i> spp.; <i>E. coli</i> ; <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ; <i>Candida albicans</i>	Bactericidal and fungicidal	[80]
Linalool	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	Antibacterial	[81]
EO*: <i>Thymus vulgaris</i> L.; <i>Thymus serpyllum</i> L.; <i>Origanum vulgare</i> L.	<i>Serratia</i> spp. and <i>Proteus</i> spp.	Antibacterial	[82]
<i>Origanum vulgare</i> L.; <i>Satureja montana</i> L. EO*	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.; <i>Streptococcus</i> spp.; <i>E. coli</i>	Antibacterial Antioxidant	[83]
<i>Melissa officinalis</i> ; <i>Menthae piperitae</i> EO*	<i>E. coli</i> , <i>Staphylococcus</i> spp., <i>Streptococcus</i> spp., <i>Enterobacter sakasakii</i> and <i>K. oxytoca</i>	Antibacterial Antioxidant	[84]
Nano-emulsions of <i>Eugenia caryophyllata</i> ; <i>Origanum vulgare</i> ; <i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> EO*	<i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>E. coli</i> ; <i>Candida albicans</i>	Antibacterial, fungicidal	[85]

*Essential oil (EO); **Plant extract (PE).

bacteria [89,90].

Phages can be classified based on various factors, including infection strategies (lytic or temperate), morphological traits and genomic aspects, leading to a diverse categorization within different families such as *Myoviridae*, *Siphoviridae* and *Podoviridae* [91,92].

In terms of infection strategies, lytic phages exclusively follow the lytic cycle in bacteria. On the other hand, temperate phages can integrate their genetic content into the hosts chromosomes and replicate as part of their genome, ultimately leading to host cell lysis. For this reason, it is crucial to characterize phages based on this aspect, selecting appropriate non-temperate lytic phages for therapeutic use [90].

The phages lytic capacity depends to a large extent on their production of endolysins or lysins, enzymes that play a crucial role in the breakdown of the host cell wall at the end of the phage replication cycle [93]. Endolysins, unlike antibiotics, have remarkable specificity, being a promising alternative to combat antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains. Furthermore, they minimize adverse effects to bovine hosts when used to treat conditions such as bovine mastitis [94,95].

Tables 6 and 7 provide a comprehensive summary of the findings from *in vitro* and *in vivo* tests evaluating the activity of bacteriophages and endolysins against bovine mastitis causing bacteria.

The lytic capacity of phages and/or lysins has been demonstrated in different bacteria such as *Staphylococcus* [90,91,94,96–100], *Streptococcus* [101,102] or *Klebsiella* [103]. Moreover, they have shown the capacity to modify the biofilm structure of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains [91,97,102,104].

In vivo studies investigating the therapeutic potential of phages or lysins for mastitis treatment have been primarily assessed in murine models through post-administration histological evaluation of the mammary glands. In this regard, the administration of *Aerococcus viridans* phage, led to bacterial count reduction and mammary tissue damage alleviation [89]. Likewise, the administration of vB_EcoM-UFV13 phage decreased the *E. coli* concentration and the proinflammatory cytokines expression together with the prevention of the biofilm formation [104]. Similar results were obtained by Teng et al. (2022) in a mastitis murine model caused by *S. aureus* [105]. Finally, an

Table 5Summary of *in vivo* assays evaluating the potential of EO* and PE** as alternatives in the treatment of bovine mastitis.

EOs/PEs	Animal model	Pathogens tested	Results	Reference
Brewers Gold; Perle hops; Propolis; Lum lichen; Common mallow; Marigold, Absinthe wormwood; Black poplar buds; Lemon balm; oregano; Lavender; Rosemary	Bovine	Different gram-positive and gram-negative strains	Bactericidal	[87]
<i>Panax ginseng</i> PE** + Cephalexin	Bovine	Non-aureus staphylococci; <i>S. aureus</i> ; <i>S. uberis</i> ; <i>S. dysgalactiae</i> ; <i>Streptococcus</i> spp.	Bactericidal	[69]
<i>Aloe vera</i> L.	Bovine	<i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial combined with low doses of antibiotics	[86]
<i>Thymus vulgaris</i> L.; <i>Thymus serpyllum</i> L.; <i>Origanum vulgare</i> L. and <i>Satureja montana</i> L. EO*	Bovine	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.; <i>Streptococcus</i> spp.; <i>Klebsiella</i> spp.; <i>Proteus mirabilis</i> ; <i>E. coli</i> ; <i>S. uberis</i> ; <i>Serratia marcescens</i>	Antibacterial	[62]

*Essential oil (EO); ** Plant extract (PE).

Table 6Summary of *in vitro* assays evaluating the potential of different bacteriophages and endolysins as alternatives in the treatment of bovine mastitis.

Bacteriophage / Lysin	Pathogens tested	Results	Reference
Lytic phages of <i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	Bacteriostatic	[103]
vB_EcoM-UVF13 phage	<i>E. coli</i> ; <i>Trueperella pyogenes</i>	Bacteriostatic Reduction of cytokines expression Antibiofilm activity	[104]
Lytic phages (SAJK-IND; MSP)	<i>S. aureus</i>	Lytic activity	[100]
Isolated phages	<i>S. aureus</i>	Lytic activity	[99]
Cocktail of phages (STA1. ST29; EB1. ST11; EB1. ST27)	<i>S. aureus</i>	Pathogen reduction	[96]
Lytic phages (SYGD1, SYGE1; SYGMH1)	<i>E. coli</i>	Pathogen reduction SCC* reduction Inflammation reduction	[88]
vB_SauM_SDQ phage	<i>S. aureus</i>	Antibiofilm	[97]
Phage 24A2	<i>S. aureus</i>	Antibacterial	[94]
<i>Staphylococcus</i> M8; B4 phages (<i>Podoviridae</i> family)	<i>S. aureus</i> resistant strains	Antibacterial and antibiofilm	[91]
<i>S. aureus</i> phages (B_UFSM4; B_UFSM5)	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	Lytic activity	[90]
PlySs2; PlySs9 endolysin	<i>S. uberis</i>	Antibacterial	[101]
LysGH15 endolysin	<i>S. aureus</i>	Bactericidal	[98]
Lysin CHAPk endolysin	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	Antibacterial and antibiofilm	[102]

* Somatic cell counts (SCC).

E. coli-induced bovine mastitis was used to evaluate the efficacy of a three-phage cocktail. The results obtained after milk analysis concluded a significant reduction in bacteria counts, SSC and inflammatory factors [88].

While results from studies utilizing bacteriophages and endolysins demonstrate promising potential for mastitis control, it is imperative to conduct further trials to fully ascertain their efficacy, particularly in bovine hosts.

2.5. Other alternatives

Other less explored approaches hold potential for the control of bovine mastitis. Inorganic nanoparticles (NPs), including gold-silver NPs, have been investigated for eradicating *S. aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* bacterial biofilms associated with mastitis. These NPs can be easily synthesized and have demonstrated *in vitro* antimicrobial effects, reducing microbial growth [108].

Also, silver and copper NPs, alone or in combination, have exhibited the ability to *in vitro* inhibit the formation of biofilms of different mastitis-causing bacteria (*Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *E. coli*, *Klebsiella*) [109]. These NPs did not show toxic effects on human or bovine mammary cells [110]. The effectiveness of copper NPs in treating mastitis was validated in murine mastitis models caused by *S. aureus*, where their IMM application resulted in a reduction of the bacterial load and improved oxidative stress levels [111]. Furthermore, the potential of polymeric NPs based on chitosan has been investigated. These NPs exhibited bactericidal activity against *Pseudomonas*, inhibited biofilm formation, and eradicated pre-existing biofilms *in vitro* [112].

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) of other origins than bacteria, can also present promising potential as alternatives to antibiotics. For instance, Polybia MP-1 obtained from the venom *Polybia paulista* wasp has demonstrated antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains isolated from mastitic cow milk [113,114].

On the other hand, caffeic acid is a phenolic compound that has been recently evaluated *in vitro*. This versatile compound exhibits notable antibacterial and antibiofilm properties, effectively limiting bacterial proliferation. Furthermore, caffeic acid has demonstrated its capacity to not only diminish *E. coli* cell adhesion and alleviate inflammation but also reduce oxidative stress in BMEC [119,120].

Mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), as well as their secretome, including extracellular vesicles (EVs), have garnered significant attention in bovine mastitis therapy. MSCs have demonstrated their capacity to modify the tissue homeostasis in *S. aureus* or *S. uberis* infections, including methicillin-resistant strains, exhibiting antimicrobial properties, and promoting tissue repair and regeneration. These effects have been observed both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [115,116]. Furthermore, inflammation was considerably improved when MSCs overexpressed angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) [117]. In a bovine model, the intramammary inoculation of both MSCs and their secreted EVs has been demonstrated to contribute to a decrease in SCC and a simultaneous increase in the expression of anti-inflammatory cytokines [118].

Other options under evaluation for mastitis treatment or prevention include antibody therapy [121]; vaccines [122] and nitric oxide-releasing formulations [123].

3. Conclusions and future perspectives

The development of AMR is a major challenge for global health, closely related to the excessive use of antibiotics in cattle, with prominence for bovine mastitis. Better protocols are needed to address this problem in practice and to explore new non-antibiotic alternatives for prevention and treatment of mastitis.

Biomimetic approaches are trending topic. The use of probiotics, bacteriocins, phytochemicals or bacteriophages gives a universe of possibilities. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the suggested alternatives, unlike traditional antibiotics, go beyond the simple goals of promoting

Table 7Summary of *in vivo* assays evaluating the potential of different bacteriophages and endolysins as alternatives in the treatment of bovine mastitis.

Bacteriophage/Lysin	Animal model	Pathogens	Sample evaluated	Evaluation time	Results and conclusions	Reference
vB_EcoM-UFV13 phage	Murine	<i>E. coli</i>	Mammary tissue	48 h	Reduction of cytokines expression	[104]
<i>S. aureus</i> phages (vBSM A1; vBSP-A2)	Murine	<i>S. aureus</i>	Mammary tissue	24 h	Pathogen reduction Symptoms improvement	[106]
<i>Aerococcus viridans</i> phage	Murine	<i>Aerococcus viridans</i>	Mammary tissue	24 h	Symptoms improvement	[89]
vB_PaeS_PAJD-1 phage	Murine	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	Mammary tissue	24 h	Pathogen reduction Symptoms improvement	[93]
CM8-1 phage	Murine	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	Mammary tissue	12, 24 and 36 h	Pathogen reduction	[107]
<i>S. aureus</i> phages (4086-1; 4086-2, 4086-3; 4086-4; 4086-6)	Murine	<i>S. aureus</i>	Mammary tissue	-	Bacteriostatic Anti-inflammatory	[105]
Lytic phages (SYGD1; SYGE1; SYGMH1)	Bovine	<i>E. coli</i>	Milk	24 h	Pathogen reduction SCC* reduction Anti-inflammatory	[88]
LysGH15 endolysin	Murine	<i>S. aureus</i>	Mammary tissue	48 h	Symptoms improvement	[98]

* Somatic cell counts (SCC).

Fig. 2. Different points targeted by biomimetic approaches under consideration.

bacterial death and reducing bacterial growth. Instead, they consider a spectrum of factors associated to host microenvironments. These biomimetic strategies present a comprehensive approach with the potential of modulating various stages of infection, encompassing the modification of the local microbiota and the immune response, preventing oxidative stress, interacting with epithelial cells, and controlling the inflammatory process. However, these strategies have only been partially explored in the veterinary field for the treatment of bovine mastitis.

Probiotics have emerged as the most researched option, showing great potential as possible alternative to antibiotics. Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies have demonstrated their antimicrobial effects, with the capacity to combat mastitis-causing pathogens, even in persistent infections, due to their antibiofilm activity. In addition, their ability to interact with the host's microbiota and epithelial cells, preventing the pathogen adhesion, makes them a good alternative for prophylaxis. Probiotics are already approved for use in the food industry, which supports their low-toxicity and safety for consumption. This eliminates concerns about potential residues in milk, a problem with the use of antibiotics. The fact that different *in vivo* trials have administered probiotics by IMM and achieved sufficient antibacterial effect, suggests that

an extremely advanced technology for administration may not be necessary. The identification of the most effective probiotic strains and the appropriate development of IMM formulations, represent the next relevant steps towards addressing bovine mastitis prevention, without requiring antibiotics.

Some bacteriocins, such as nisin, are already marketed as a teat disinfectant. They are effective at low concentrations, but also vulnerable to resistances development. The main advantages of these products are their antibacterial activity at low concentrations, their easier metabolism compared to classical antibiotics and the possibility of modification by bioengineering. On the other hand, its administration is hampered by the lack of stability associated to the protein nature, which makes impossible to use certain administration routes. This explains the limited number of *in vivo* studies. To overcome this limitation, nanotechnology is proposed as a promising formulation strategy.

Plant-derived products offer a wide array of options for obtaining antimicrobials. PEs and EOs can be used as holistic systems with antibacterial activity, alongside with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, effectively addressing the concomitant oxidative stress and inflammation in bovine mastitis. Plant-derived products offer numerous advantages over other alternatives in the short-term development of pharmaceutical formulations for the management of bovine mastitis. They are easily accessible, require less specific production and have greater stability compared to probiotics, bacteriocins or bacteriophages.

Specific species can be cultivated for their production, nevertheless phytochemicals can also be obtained as by-products of other industries. By establishing a connection between the waste-chain and livestock industries, it is possible to promote the circular economy while simultaneously enhancing animal health and welfare, and without resorting to antibiotics.

Bacteriophages and their endolysins also constitute a wide spectrum of possibilities, not only in the therapy of bovine mastitis, but also in many other pathologies. They are abundant in nature and highly specific, limiting the possibility of developing resistance and avoiding adverse side effects.

Several bacteriophages and endolysins have been isolated and successfully characterized *in vitro* as antibacterials for bovine mastitis pathogens. Despite their promising prospects, the number of *in vivo* assays is much more limited and, moreover, studies have mainly been carried out in murine models, thus further investigation in this field is necessary. The development of pharmaceutical formulations for use in bovine mastitis therapy should also be addressed.

Overall, only few studies have finally developed formulations with potential clinical applications for these alternatives. While numerous *in vitro* studies support their properties, there is a lack of *in vivo* research,

particularly, in bovine hosts to confirm their efficacy and security.

Ultimately, achieving significant progress in the clinic requires the obtention of stable pharmaceutical formulations containing the proposed alternatives. In the pursuit of this objective, bacteriocins seems to be the active ingredients with most notable limitations due to their instability. Although probiotics and bacteriophages have been tested *in vivo*, their incorporation into pharmaceutical formulations remains underexplored. However, plant extracts and essential oils have a significant advantage in this context.

Future steps ought to be focused on developing formulations with suitable physicochemical properties for their administration into the mammary gland. Leveraging pharmaceutical development would ensure precise local drug delivery, optimal retention time at the site of action and consequently, the enhancement of the therapeutic efficacy. Given the current scenario, plant extracts and essential oils emerge as the most promising short-term alternatives.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Lara Touza-Otero: Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Mariana Landin:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Patricia Diaz-Rodriguez:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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